

TIP-N-POINT: a regional and assemblage scale perspective on Neanderthal point technologies across Western Europe

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Stone-tipped hunting weapons are an important marker of the technical and cognitive capacities of Palaeolithic hominins and represent a crucial tipping point in human behavioural evolution. Neanderthals were skilled hunters, as indicated by zooarchaeological and isotope analyses, but preserved remains of organic spears are sparse and potential lithic weapon tips are not ubiquitously present during the Middle Palaeolithic (MP, ca. 300,000 - 40,000BP). Unravelling this enigma and reconstructing the technology underlying MP hunting events is one of the key challenges in studies of Neanderthal behaviour. Securely identifying hafted weapon tips is complex and past analyses of MP points have mainly focused on individual artefacts, their morphometric characteristics, use-wear and residue traces. Conversely, studies that contextualise MP points at an assemblage level, cross comparing various blank and tool types, are sparse, especially for the European record, even though they are key to a more comprehensive understanding of the role of point shapes in the Neanderthal tool kit. This poster presents two sets of initial results of this Marie Curie-Sklodawska funded project. Firstly, at the regional scale, it outlines the occurrence and typo-technological characteristics of point shapes across MP assemblages in western Europe. Results indicate the low presence of triangular forms in many Middle Palaeolithic assemblages but also their more common occurrence in certain specific spatio-temporal entities (e.g. MIS-5 northern France or MIS-3 south-eastern France). Secondly, initial results from an assemblage level study of the lithic material from layer 1 of the Abri du Maras rockshelter (MIS-3, Southeastern France) are presented. Focus was on the material from the 1946-1950 excavation by R. Gilles which resulted in a lithic collection of around 3,000 artefacts. Past studies have pointed out the presence of several pointed flakes with convergent ventral retouch, assigning the assemblage to the so-called Neronian, a late Middle Paleolithic entity only known from the Rhone valley. A detailed attribute analysis focused on the recording across all blanks of a series of features which have been linked to projectile use or hafting (e.g. diagnostic impact fracture, lateral crushing, basal modifications). Results indicate a large variability in the convergent tools, both in terms of blank type (Levallois, discoidal and laminar flaking) as well as retouch extent and location. This poster will further present and cross compare these points within the context of the rest of the assemblage.